
A journey of psychic upheaval to Independence of women in Sudha Murthy's novel '*Mahashweta*'

Dr. Sandeep Kumar, Assistant Professor in English, GCW Gohana (Sonapat)

Paper Received on 01-04-2023, Accepted on 22-05-2023,
Published on 24-05-23; DOI: 10.36993/ RJOE.2023.8.95

Abstract

Sudha Murthy is a well-known name of India. She has written many books based on Human Relationship children and women. The novel focuses mainly on women's problems related to their relationship with husband and in-laws. She has been awarded by many prestigious awards. Her novels, *Gently Falls the Bakula*, *Dollar Bahu* and *Mahashweta* revolve around the women's mental conflict that arises in marriage. Despite their full involvement and devotion, they face many miserable conditions at every turn of their life and are ultimately forced to leave their husband's house. For an independent life, they make bold decisions to leave their house because nobody understands their mental condition and miserable life due to her disease, and decide not to engage in a marriage again. She never accepts the marriage proposal she received. The clearest example of how to refute prevalent misunderstandings about women and highlight their value to society is found in Sudha Murthy's "Mahashweta." In the oppressive patriarchal society, the protagonist yearns for identity and makes a fresh stride and starts towards liberation. This process ultimately results in independence to varying degrees.

Keywords: Women, Conflict, Independent, Marriage.

Mahashweta is among the best novels that illustrate to society the determination of women in forging their own identities. Mahashweta successfully refutes the widespread belief that men can have an influence over women. The main character defies society's psychology and loses sight of who she is and where she fits in. Husbands keep their identities a secret, but throw women in condition of psychic upheaval despite their hard work.

The idea of the new woman is embodied by Mahashweta, the protagonist who questions the idea of human dominance in society and creates her own identity. The hardship of women with skin diseases that result in colour changes in their skin receives the majority of the novel Mahashweta's attention. She visited a dermatologist due to the change in the hue of her skin, which changed her life, destroyed her happiness, and left her all alone in the world. Even her husband, in whom she has the greatest faith because he is a physician, refused to help her. Because

of the trauma in her life, she has learned that no one will step forward to help her, so she decides to work for her own money. The doctor predicts that she won't have any skin issues in the future, but her husband won't like her because he chose her. Anupama's husband falls in love with her because of her beauty, but when the same attractiveness causes rashes to appear on her body, he grows frustrated and decides to leave.

This mentality of guys who think they are superior in society is criticised by the author.

In contrast to huddling and praying for her life, the author's portrayal of a woman shows her rebelling against male domination and losing sight of who she is. The end of the article mentions that Anupama's husband is willing to accept her, but she denies the assertion. In the first few pages of the book, the author discusses Anupama, one of the prettiest girls in the city. She has dedicated her life to social service, and she supports charitable trusts with the money she makes from her theatre company. In order to gather as much money as she can for the trust fund, she sells show tickets door to door. She is a beautiful young woman who is also a gifted singer and theatre performer. At Dr. Desai's house, she meets Anand, and their encounter changes her life and sparks their romance. The fact that Dr. Anand came from a rich family made it easy for him to get her ready for marriage. Anupama concurred, believing that this was the best marriage proposal ever.

Dr. Anand has a sister named Girija in addition to his mother Radhakka.

Anupama's life was not entirely rosy before to getting married because of how her stepmother and stepsister treated her. Before she got married, her two sisters competed for her affection, and Girija continues to do so today.

Due to his financial status, Dr. Anand is happy to cover all expenses, which is acceptable to both sides. Anupama's father and Anupama only experienced this ecstasy in comparable circumstances due to her stepmother's strong dissatisfaction at watching their extravagant wedding. According to Murthy's tale, Anupama has the best spouse to take care of her. The author describes Anupama's husband as wanting to go abroad for higher studies in the future.

Dr. Anand decides to pursue his education in England after their marriage, leaving Anupama to care for her mother-in-law on her own. Because Girija is very liberal, Mother-in-Law is quite domineering, and Anupama is very subservient, these three women are currently very unhappy at home. Anupama feels lonely at home due to her husband being out of India. Gradually, her mental condition goes through a severe condition due to her skin disease and in-laws' behaviour, always trying to down her in every situation. Anupama finds herself in psychic upheaval.

As a result, Anand declines to help her during her husband-and-wife separation and keeps a low profile. The wealthy society considers Anupama's purity to make her an unfit woman, therefore her mother starts hunting for another girl for her son Anand. Anupama decides to commit suicide

after contemplating it while depressed. The idea of this challenge entered Anupama's mind, but she was at a loss for new things to reflect on in her life. She remembers how in the theatre days, there was always a happy ending, but her life was about to end. Anupama decides to leave the house in one of the incidents in the book, which is her first step towards independent.

Anupama, a bride, comes to the opinion that she shouldn't be able to locate a wealthy partner for marriage if her sister-in-law, who has multiple relationships, lives a great life and does so. when she leads an ethical life. The brave woman decides to make her own sacrifices in order to live a happy and honourable life right away after considering suicide. A new lady is being born at this time.

Anupama went to her room, collected the few things that belonged to her, picked up one of Anand's photographs and returned where Shamanna waited for her. She took his hand in hers, and silently clutching her bag, walked out of the house. She knew in her heart that this was the last time she would be seeing the house or its people...but she did not look back even once. (59)

She decides to disregard all the mocking and leaves for Bombay in order to find work and live independently. Anupama's life in Bombay had to change because she was forced to leave her friend Sumithra's home because of her husband's altered behaviour towards her. Currently, she lives with her close friend Sumi and works as a Sanskrit instructor at a nearby

college. Even Dr. Vasanth's recommendation is turned down. She says she doesn't want to accept the offer since she is tired of the family's prejudice.

When Vasant requests to marry her, she denies very clearly: "I don't want to get entangle again in the same circle of husband and family. My past had taught me a very valuable lesson." (MS 150)

Vasant's friend Satya says, "I respect Anupama a lot. She is such a balanced person. Even with all the odds stacked against her, she is always optimistic. Life has treated her badly and given her so many shocks, but she is never bitter." (MS 136)

Anupama demonstrates the transformation of a new independent woman within herself by refusing to participate in the institution of marriage and breaks the deep-rooted chain of psychic upheaval of women. She exemplifies how a woman is capable of pursuing her own goals without a man's support. Anupama finally gains the confidence to design a picture of the self-reliant, independent woman of the new millennium who is free from the dread of the patriarchal system.

References:

- Murty Sudha. *Mahashweta*. New Delhi: Penguin Books.2007. Print.
 Parvathi, S. and S.K. Pushpalata. "THE EVOLUTION OF A NEW WOMAN IN THE SUDHA MURTHY'S NOVEL 'MAHASHWETA.'" *Research Journal of English Language and Literature (RJELAL)*, vol. 4, no. 1, Apr. 2016, doi:10.33329/rjelal. Accessed 13 May 2023

How to cite this article?

Dr. Sandeep Kumar “ A journey of psychic upheaval to Independence of women in Sudha Murty's novel ‘Mahashweta’” Research Journal Of English (RJOE)8(2), PP:96-99-2023, DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.2.99